

There are three species of bear native to North America. Most numerous North American bears. The most common is the American black bear, followed by the brown bear and then the polar bear. Discovered throughout Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Weighs 200 to 600 pounds. Could be dark or light brown (cinnamon), typically even white. Not at all times black in shade. 900,000 and not threatened. □□ Location: The American black bear can be found throughout Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Nonetheless, some subspecies such as the Louisiana black bear are protected below the U.S. □□ Dimension: Adults weigh 200 to 600 pounds and are 5 to 6 toes in length. □□ Options: Most black bears are black, however their fur can range from darkish brown to lighter brown (cinnamon) and even white on uncommon occasions. They have pointed ears and a straight face. Of all of the bear species black bears are a few of the perfect at climbing timber. Their comparatively smaller dimension and shorter claws make them fast and nimble to climb timber for protection, meals, and even hibernation. The majority of their weight loss program is vegetarian consisting of berries, plant shoots, and nuts. □□ Diet: Their different food plan offers them the ability to dwell in a large vary of habitats. Additionally they eat insects, fish, and carrion. □□ Harmful? They are the probably bear to be encountered within the backcountry. And yes, they love [small teddy bear online](#)

honey. The grizzly and Kodiak are the 2 subspecies of brown bears in North America. Most widespread bear species are found within the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Middle East. Brown bears are the most widespread of all bear species, discovered in the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Center East. Grizzlies are responsible for almost all bear attacks in North America, with 46 per 12 months. Though their conservation standing is "least concern", their unfold-out nature and lowered habitat make lots of the small remaining pockets fragile. The 200,000 brown bears of the world occupy a wide variety of habitats spanning deserts, forests, and mountains. All brown bears share a big construct, a dish-formed face, and a shoulder hump. Their hair is lighter at the tips, which led to the identify of the most famous subspecies, grizzly. Brown bears forage on roots, berries, insects, and fish, and some even hunt younger mammals such as elk and moose. Their color varies from mild blonde to dark brown. The 2 subspecies in North America are the grizzly and Kodiak. □□ Location: Grizzly bears are discovered within the northern USA, Canada, and Alaska. □□ Size: Adults weigh four hundred to 790 pounds, are 6.5 ft long, and have a shoulder peak of 3.3 ft. □□ Diet: Grizzlies eat berries, nuts, salmon and have been identified to prey on giant mammals. Coastal grizzlies tend to be bigger than these discovered within the Rocky Mountains on account of a richer weight loss plan. Annually there are 46 assaults and 6 deaths. □□ Harmful? Recognized for their aggressive behavior, grizzlies are liable for probably the most bear attacks in North America. □□ Location: Kodiak bears are solely found on the Kodiak Islands, an archipelago in southwestern Alaska. □□ Dimension: Kodiak bears are nearly as massive as polar bears, weighing 600 to 1,400 pounds, 8 toes long, and 4 toes tall on the shoulder. □□ Weight loss program: Their food regimen is just like mainland grizzly bears. Nevertheless, on account of more plentiful food sources, the islands can support a denser bear population. Geographic isolation from the mainland allowed the 3,500 Kodiak bears to change into their own subspecies. This has led to a more complicated social structure which ends up in less battle between bears. □□ Harmful? Like grizzlies, Kodiak bears may be aggressive. Attributable to their isolation, there is just one assault on humans each other year. Largest species of bear in the world weighing between 800 and 1,300 pounds. Food plan is usually made up of meat, usually from seals. □□ Location: Polar bears are the biggest bears and largest land carnivores on the planet. Fur seems white however is definitely clear. The world's 20,000 to 30,000 polar bears range in the snow-covered arctic ice in Alaska, Canada, Russia, and Norway. □□ Size: Adult polar bears are 800 to 1,300 pounds and might be 7 to 10 ft tall. They're a threatened species due to lack of habitat from local weather change. Despite their huge dimension polar bears may be quick, maintaining a 6 mph tempo within the water. □□ Features: Compared to different bears, polar bears have a slimmer body, slender head, longer neck, and paddle-like paws. For context, swimmer Michael Phelps gained Olympic gold medals with a 4.7 mph tempo! □□ Diet: Their weight-reduction plan consists largely of animals, especially seals which they'll odor from a mile away. Though they seem white, their fur is actually clear and their skin is black. □□ Dangerous? Polar bears may be extremely harmful. They see humans as potential prey. Assaults are uncommon because of the remote nature of their habitat. Recognized for its cream colour chest blazes. At 300 pounds one of many smaller bears. Straightforward to tame and often widespread in circuses. □□ Location: The Asian black bear is present in forests and shrublands throughout Asia from Iran to Japan. The population is estimated at 40,000 to 50,000 and is taken into account susceptible. □□ Dimension: One of many smaller species, adults weigh round 300 pounds and stand

forty seven to seventy five inches tall. □□ Food regimen: Depending on the season it generally feeds on small mammals, birds, fish, mollusks and carcasses or grasses, fruits, berries, seeds, insects, and honey. Assaults on humans are rising as individuals encroach on their habitat. □□ Dangerous? They are one in all the best bears to tame (and therefore common in circuses), but Asian black bears are more aggressive than their North American counterparts. Discovered only in China. 99% of its eating regimen is bamboo. In reality, the second particular person in history to receive a facial transplant was mauled by an Asian black bear while defending his sheep. Recognized for its iconic white face, eye patches, and striped physique. □□ Location: Pandas are found only in China. Only 1,500 to 2,000 stay within the wild and they're thought-about a vulnerable species. □□ Measurement: Pandas weigh round 300 pounds and could be over four feet tall, an impressive feat contemplating they weigh only about 3.5 ounces at beginning. It also has a close cousin, the Qinling panda which has the identical sample in mild brown and white. □□ Weight loss plan: Not like other bears the panda's food plan is homogeneous; 99% of what they eat is bamboo. □□ Features: The large panda is iconic for its white face, black eye patches, and striped body. All that fibrous bamboo keeps them common: they poop over forty times a day! □□ Dangerous? Assaults are rare however harmful, given that pandas have one in every of the best chunk forces of any carnivore. Smallest Bear weighing fifty five to 143 pounds. Found in South East Asia. Eight to 10-inch lengthy tongue for slurping up insects and honey. □□ Location: The Sun bear is found within the forest and shrubland of South East Asia and India. It is the least studied bear and. Its inhabitants is uncertain however thought-about weak and on the decline as a result of lack of habitat and poaching. Solar bears are hunted for his or her gallbladders and other physique elements utilized in traditional medicines. □□ Measurement: They stand only 39 to fifty five inches and weigh fifty five to 143 pounds making them the smallest bear. □□ Options: Solar bears have strongly curved claws, small rounded ears, and a short snout. They're named for their pale, horseshoe-shaped chest patch that looks like a rising sun. They also eat seeds, fruit, birds, and deer. □□ Food plan: Sun bears tear apart bushes and nests to eat ants, bees, beetles, termites, and honey. Their love of honey has given them the nickname "honey bears." Actually, they've an extremely long tongue (8-10 inches) for slurping up insects and honey. Native to South Asia. □□ Harmful? Because of its shy nature, attacks are rare. Lengthy, shaggy fur and mane gave them the name sloth bear. Sloth bears are feared by rhinos and elephants. □□ Location: The Sloth bear is discovered in the low elevation savanna and shrubland of India, Nepal, and Sri Lanka. With a declining population of less than 20,000, they are thought of vulnerable. □□ Size: They are 55 to 75 inches long and weigh 200 to 300 pounds. □□ Options: With their long shaggy fur and mane, they're straightforward to tell aside from other Asiatic bears. In actuality, they're very fast and might out-gallop humans. European explorers mistook them for sloths after seeing them hanging the wrong way up from timber. They are noisy, messy eaters tearing up termite mounds with their large curved claws. □□ Weight loss program: Their food plan consists of termites, ants, and fruit. □□ Harmful? They are one of the most aggressive bears, with essentially the most assaults on humans, principally resulting from shock encounters. They blow the mud round with big puffs and suck the ants up so loudly they are often heard 600 toes away. Sloth bears stand their ground if threatened and don't mix effectively with rhinos and elephants, typically charging at one another when in proximity. Solely South American bear. World's final short-faced bear. The name "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings around their eyes that appear to be glasses. This weak species of 13,000 to 18,000 remaining bears are found in the cloud forests of the Andes from Argentina to Ecuador. □□ Dimension: They are mid-sized, weighing 175 to 275 pounds, and standing 47 to 79 inches tall. □□ Location: The spectacled bear is the world's last quick-faced bear and the only bear native to South America. □□ Options: The identify "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings around their eyes that sometimes appear to be glasses. They spend most of their time in bushes the place they construct nest platforms, sleep and jealously guard treasured fruit and carcasses. □□ Weight-reduction plan: Spectacled bears are principally herbivores with a diet consisting of principally cactus, bromeliad, palm hearts, and fruit, however they will opportunistically eat mammals like rabbits and tapirs. □□ Dangerous? Residing in remote mountains, these shy bears may be the least dangerous of all bear species. Their bodies are smaller than polar bears but bigger than grizzlies. The Grolar bear (aka Pizzly) is a uncommon hybrid of a polar bear and a grizzly bear that happens in both nature and captivity. Grolar bear conduct is closer to the polar bear. They function the lengthy necks of polar bears and the shoulder humps of grizzlies. In captivity, they've been documented stomping toys, just like how polar bears break ice. Black-brown hybrid bears have been bred in captivity, notably on the London Zoo in 1859, however haven't been confirmed within the wild. In 1986, a suspected grizzly-brown hybrid was shot however DNA checks were unable to find out what type of bear it was. Adorable koalas aren't bears, they're burly marsupials. Water bears aren't bears both, they are indestructible, microscopic animals that can survive in area. Most bear assaults occur when a bear is

startled or protecting their cubs. Crimson pandas? They're in their own household that are closer cousins with skunks and raccoons than bears.

1. **BEWARE OF YOUR SURROUNDINGS.** Watch for bear scat and bear tracks that may indicate a bear is nearby, in which case you wish to be extra vigilant. Here are a number of ideas you can use to forestall bear encounters and keep you and your hiking buddies safe.
2. **MAKE NOISE.** This helps bears know you're here so they don't accidentally startle them. Consider attaching a bear bell to your pack.
3. **KEEP YOUR DISTANCE.** Whereas you might have nice intentions, a bear is prone to feel threatened when it sees you approaching and defend itself.
3. **Safe YOUR SCENTED Gadgets (AT CAMP).** When you see a bear, don't attempt to approach or feed it. This includes meals, but additionally your toiletries, for instance. Whichever methodology you choose, be certain it is a minimum of 200 ft away from your tent so you do not entice bears to your campsite.
4. **Stay CALM.** In case you meet a bear, do not run. Attempt to make your self look as huge as attainable, waving your arms above your head. You may as well prolong a jacket above your head to make yourself look larger. Lock these things in a bear canister or use a bear bag to cling them up in a tree. Don't scream or try to scare the bear.
5. **USE BEAR SPRAY (AS A last RESORT).** Communicate to it calmly and slowly back away. Full instruction on how to use bear spray right here. If the bear is dangerously close (30 toes) or is charging at you, pull out your bear spray and use it in 1-2 second bursts, aiming barely downward.
6. **Struggle Again.** If all else fails and a bear assaults you, don't play dead. Which bear is the most important? Averaging 900-1500 lbs, 8.0 to 8.4 toes lengthy, and 4.0 to 5.25 ft tall, the most important bear by each measurement and weight is the polar bear. The largest ever recorded was 2,200 lbs. Combat back with all of your strength and hope that it will back down. Which bear is the most dangerous? All bears are harmful if provoked. Globally, the Asian black bear is known for essentially the most assaults. When in bear country, it's at all times wise to hold bear spray. It's effectively deserved, especially when cubs are around. Annually there are roughly forty six grizzly attacks, 6 leading to loss of life. In North America, grizzly bears have the most fearsome fame. Which bear is the strongest? Whereas you're most more likely to see an American black bear, on average there is only one assault per yr. In terms of uncooked chew power, measured in Newtons, the polar bear's chew reigns supreme. All bears are robust and to not be messed with. When using the chunk pressure quotient (chunk power relative to dimension), the solar bear packs the most punch. Originally named "Hotfoot Teddy", Smokey Bear was a black bear cub discovered in the spring of 1950 after a wildfire in New Mexico. He had climbed a tree to escape the fire but sustained burns on his paws and hind legs. Soon after he turned an icon and to this day is the star of the longest-operating public service announcement campaign. Yogi Bear is an animated bear known for his love of "pic-a-nic" baskets. Extra importantly Yogi Bear has inspired numerous via-hikers to attempt to grasp the artwork of "yogi-ing", the act of not fairly begging but receiving favors from strangers. Baloo s a sloth bear, though he has some characteristics of the Asian black bear. He's an easygoing, friendly bear who lives a accountability-free lifestyle. He also is perhaps the primary bear to obtain his pilot's license. Before he was the storybook teddy bear, Winnie the Pooh was a black bear from Canada which the author's son typically would visit at the London Zoo. Winnie is brief for "Winnipeg," the town in Canada close to where he was from. Chris additionally wrote The right way to Hike the Appalachian Path. Equal components backpacking meals and ultralight gear. After thru-hiking the Appalachian Trail, Chris Cage created Greenbelly to provide quick, filling and balanced meals to backpackers. Get epic tips, guides and how-to's in your inbox each two weeks.

